

IONIC REACTIONS IN THIONYL CHLORIDE PART I: COMPLEXES OF SOLVO-ACIDS AND ANSOLVO-BASES

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Thionyl chloride, a polar solvent, has been employed as a medium for ionic reactions between ansolvo-bases and solvo-acids. Quaternary ammonium chlorides, such as, tetramethylammonium chloride, trimethylphenylammonium chloride, trimethylbenzylammonium chloride, dimethylphenylbenzylammonium chloride and triethylbenzylammonium chloride, react with solutions of titanium tetrachloride, zirconium tetrachloride and stannic chloride in thionyl chloride to yield normal complexes of the general formula :

The complexes of triethylbenzylammonium chloride with the aforementioned acids, which are highly soluble in thionyl chloride, have been separated out by the addition of dry ethyl acetate to the reaction mixture.

Formation of the complexes of zirconium tetrachloride with trimethylbenzylammonium chloride and triethylbenzylammonium chloride has also been studied by the conductometric method.

The formation of these complexes and changes in conductance have been explained on the basis of the ionisation of thionyl chloride and ionic species formed by the ionisation of ansolvo-bases and solvo-acids in thionyl chloride solutions.

Thionyl chloride possesses a fairly high value of dipole moment (1.60 *D* at 20°; Beyaert and Govaert, *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, 32, 6517), comparatively long and polar sulphur—chlorine bond (2.07 Å, expected 2.04 Å; Palmer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2360; Allen and Sutton, *Acta Cryst.*, 1950, 3, 46) and relatively high value of dielectric constant (9.25 at 20°; Beyaert and Govaert, *loc. cit.*). It has a convenient working range of temperature (m.p.-104.5°, b.p. 78.8°; Mayes and Partington, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2594; Thorpe, *ibid.*, 1880, 37, 141; 1882, 41, 297) and its electrical conductivity (2.0 × 10⁻⁶ at 25°; Walden, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1900, 25, 209) is higher than that of acetyl chloride (4.0 × 10⁻⁷ at 25°; Walden, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, 54, 128). All these properties, which are comparable to those of other polar solvents, inspire a study of ionic reactions in this liquid. The ionisation of thionyl chloride has been indisputably established by conductometric and potentiometric work (Spandau and Brunneck, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1952, 270, 201; 1955, 278, 193). More recently the radioactive chlorine exchange studies have also confirmed (Masters *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 4252) that ionisation of thionyl chloride can undoubtedly be expressed as :

In the present investigations, ionic reactions involving solvo-acids and ansolvo-bases have been studied. Titanium tetrachloride, stannic chloride and zirconium tetrachloride, which ordinarily possess tetrahedral structure (Lister and Sutton, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1941, 37, 393) have an inherent tendency to acquire more stable octahedral configuration by the acceptance of two chloride ions to form the ion MCl_6^{2-} (Dickinson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 276). In thionyl chloride these chlorides dissolve, to form solvo-acids of the type $MCl_4 \cdot 2SOCl_2$. The existence of $TiCl_4 \cdot 2SOCl_2$ has been reported on the basis of thermal analysis (Sheldon and Tyree, *ibid.*, 1959, 81, 2790) while the formation of similar compounds by stannic chloride and zirconium tetrachloride is presumed in solution. Stannic chloride (Walden, *loc. cit.*, 1900) and titanium tetrachloride (Klingorn, *Ukrain. Khim. Zhur.*, 1950, 16, 404; *Chem. Abs.*, 1954, 48 3775), which are non-conductors of electricity, have dipole moment almost equal to zero (Ulich *et al.*, *Z. physikal.*

Chem., 1932, **B17**, 369). However, these yield solutions in thionyl chloride which are much more conducting than the pure solvent (Spandau and Brunneck, *loc. cit.*, 1952). Zirconium tetrachloride dissolves in thionyl chloride to form a solution which is more conducting as compared to the pure solvent. The increase in electrical conductivity of their solutions in thionyl chloride may be explained on the basis of ionisation of the solvo-acids formed in solutions.

The ansolvo-bases, which have been employed to study the complexes of these solvo-acids, are: tetramethylammonium chloride, trimethylphenylammonium chloride, trimethylbenzylammonium chloride, dimethylphenylbenzylammonium chloride and triethylbenzylammonium chloride. The mode of ionisation of these bases in thionyl chloride may be exemplified by tetramethylammonium chloride.

Ordinarily the solutions of quaternary ammonium chlorides containing methyl groups and that of titanium tetrachloride in thionyl chloride react to form yellow precipitates when the amounts of ansolvo-bases and the solvo-acid are taken in a molar ratio of 2:1 respectively. However, triethylbenzylammonium chloride and titanium tetrachloride in thionyl chloride react to yield a clear solution, and even on cooling, no solid separates. Fortunately, the addition of dry ethyl acetate helps in obtaining a solid mass which is filtered and kept under vacuum to remove the last traces of the solvents. Its analysis led to the composition of the normal complex $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5]_2\text{TiCl}_6$. The formation of these acid-base complexes is explained on the basis of ionic species which already exist in thionyl chloride solutions. For instance, the formation of $[(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}]_2\text{TiCl}_6$ may be represented as:

The precipitation of the normal complex helps the reaction to proceed to completion.

Zirconium tetrachloride, which is fairly soluble (1-2%) in thionyl chloride, reacts with the quaternary ammonium chlorides, excepting triethylbenzylammonium chloride, in thionyl chloride to yield precipitates of the normal complexes. However, the striking influence of ethyl group on the solubility of the normal complex of zirconium tetrachloride and triethylbenzylammonium chloride in thionyl chloride is illustrated by the non-precipitation of the complex when the reactants are mixed together. Here again, dry ethyl acetate has been used to precipitate out the normal complex. Nevertheless, doubt may be entertained regarding the formation of this normal complex as both of the reactants are ordinarily solids and dry ethyl acetate may have thrown out the original substances which happen to be in solution in a stoichiometric composition. In view of this observation, the formation of this complex has been studied by conductometric method.

Fig. 1 records the curves representing the conductometric titrations of trimethylbenzylammonium chloride (I) and triethylbenzylammonium chloride (II) with zirconium tetrachloride in thionyl chloride solutions. The addition of zirconium tetrachloride solution in thionyl chloride to that of trimethylbenzylammonium chloride (I) lowers the conductance of the latter and, simultaneously, appearance of a white turbidity is observed. Further addition of the acid solution brings about an increase in the amount of the precipitate of the complex, and as a consequence, the conductance records a further fall which continues up to the break represented by the acid/base molar ratio

of 1 : 2. This point indicates the completion of the reaction, maximum of precipitation and minimum of conductance. The decrease in the value of conductance with the formation of normal complex is due to removal of the more mobile chloride ions which combine with thionylum ions provided by the acid solution to form solvent molecules. The course of the reaction may be represented as :

FIG. 1

1. ZrCl_4 against trimethylbenzylammonium chloride
2. " " triethylbenzylammonium chloride

Any further addition of the acid solution increases the conductance of the solution which is due to the increase brought in the concentration of thionylum ions. This may be either effected by the dissolution of the normal complex to form acid complex $[(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_7\text{H}_7](\text{SOCl})\text{ZrCl}_6$ and its subsequent ionisation, or by the ionised solvo-acid which is being added to the reaction mixture. However, the precipitate does not dissolve completely and there is no indication as to the existence of the acid complex.

The titration of triethylbenzylammonium chloride (II) and zirconium tetrachloride in thionyl chloride records similar changes in conductance when the acid solution is added to that of the an-solvo-base in thionyl chloride. Of course, the only conspicuous difference in this titration is the complete solubility of the normal complex. During the course of this titration, the solution remains clear and decrease in conductance is explained as due to the removal of more mobile chloride ions which are taken up by thionylum ions, added to the solution, to form undissociated solvent

molecules. The conductance of the normal complex is expressed by the break at acid/base molar ratio of 1 : 2. Here the formation of normal complex is complete and, any further addition of the acid solution increases the conductance of the solution. Again, there is no indication as to the existence of the acid complex because of the continued increase of conductance without any break at acid/base molar ratio of 1 : 1. It is quite clear from these curves that break as to the formation of normal complex occurs at a much high value of conductance when the normal complex is soluble. This difference in the value of conductance at these breaks is ascribed to the ionisation of the complex, which is more soluble in thionyl chloride.

The solutions of stannic chloride in thionyl chloride react with that of tetramethylammonium chloride, trimethylphenylammonium chloride, trimethylbenzylammonium chloride and dimethylphenylbenzylammonium chloride in thionyl chloride to yield normal complexes when equivalent amounts of the reactants are employed. Of course, the solutions of stannic chloride and triethylbenzylammonium chloride in thionyl chloride react to yield a clear solution. Dry ethyl acetate was employed to precipitate out the normal complex from the reaction mixture, and prior to analysis the traces of the solvents were removed under vacuum. The formation of these complexes of stannic chloride in thionyl chloride may be illustrated by interpreting the course of reaction of dimethylphenylbenzylammonium chloride and stannic chloride in thionyl chloride as :

The precipitation of the normal complex helps the equilibrium to shift towards completion of the reaction.

TABLE I

Complex.	M.P.	Colour.	%Metal.		%Chlorine.		%Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
$[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}]_2\text{TiCl}_4$	310°(d)*	Pale yellow	11.96	11.73	52.00	52.08	6.92	6.85
$[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5]_2\text{TiCl}_4$	165°(d)	Do	9.33	9.01	39.99	39.96	5.45	5.25
$[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_7\text{H}_7]_2\text{TiCl}_4$	183°(d)	Yellow	8.77	8.55	37.21	37.96	4.85	4.99
$[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{C}_7\text{H}_7]_2\text{TiCl}_4$	175°(d)	Greenish yellow	7.08	7.01	31.41	31.10	4.56	4.08
$[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_7\text{H}_7]_2\text{TiCl}_4$	125°	Dirty yellow	7.25	7.44	33.36	33.72	4.28	4.34
$[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}]_2\text{ZrCl}_4$	322°(d)*	Dirty white	20.59	20.13	46.62	47.13	6.07	6.19
$[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5]_2\text{ZrCl}_4$	285°(d)	White	16.56	16.80	36.95	36.98	4.69	4.86
$[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_7\text{H}_7]_2\text{ZrCl}_4$	225°(d)	Do	14.84	15.07	34.87	35.27	4.53	4.63
$[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{C}_7\text{H}_7]_2\text{ZrCl}_4$	217°(d)	Do	12.55	12.50	29.24	29.26	4.03	3.85
$[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_7\text{H}_7]_2\text{ZrCl}_4$	175°(d)	Do	13.20	13.22	30.80	30.96	4.09	4.07
$[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}]_2\text{SnCl}_4$	320°(d)*	Do	24.36	24.75	44.01	44.41	6.10	5.83
$[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5]_2\text{SnCl}_4$	250°(d)	Do	20.01	19.65	35.36	35.27	4.89	4.64
$[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_7\text{H}_7]_2\text{SnCl}_4$	265°(d)	Do	18.36	18.78	33.45	33.70	4.56	4.43
$[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{C}_7\text{H}_7]_2\text{SnCl}_4$	212°(d)	Do	15.68	15.70	27.81	28.18	3.70	3.71
$[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_7\text{H}_7]_2\text{SnCl}_4$	200°	Do	16.70	16.59	30.05	29.77	4.17	3.91

* These compounds decompose without melting while others form coloured liquids on melting.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thionyl chloride (commercial grade) was distilled and the fraction boiling at 74-76° was collected. This sample was then treated with 2% quinoline and refractionated in an all-glass apparatus equipped with a vacuum jacketed fractionating column to provide a liquid of b.p. 75.5°/732mm.

For use in acid-base reactions, this liquid was further refractionated in an all-glass assembly and the fraction at take-off ratio of 1:10 was collected. This liquid was transferred to reaction tubes equipped with standard joint glass-stoppers under pressure by dry nitrogen to avoid its contact with atmospheric air.

Zirconium tetrachloride, supplied by Johnson Matthey and Co. Ltd., London, was used without any further treatment, while stannic chloride and titanium tetrachloride were redistilled over tin pieces (A.R.) and copper turnings respectively in an all-glass apparatus. The fractions boiling at 112.5-113°/743mm and 130°/745mm respectively were collected. All the quaternary ammonium chlorides employed in these investigations were crystallised from usual solvents before use the purity was checked by chemical analysis.

The general procedure for the preparation of these complexes consisted in reacting quantities of the tetrachloride and quaternary ammonium chloride in a molar ratio of 1:2 in thionyl chloride and solutions of these substances were prepared in a minimum quantity of the solvent. During the preparation of all these complexes care was taken to add acid solutions to that of base in thionyl chloride just to avoid contamination of any acid complex, which may otherwise be formed. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand in an ice-bath for about 45 minutes so as to complete the reaction. Filtration of the precipitate was carried in a sintered glass funnel kept in a special assembly which avoided contact of moisture. All these materials were kept under vacuum before analysis so that occluded solvents should be completely removed. Dry ethyl acetate was employed to precipitate out the complexes of triethylbenzylammonium chloride which were highly soluble in thionyl chloride.

Titanium, zirconium and tin were weighed as dioxides while chlorine was estimated by Volhard's method. The analysis of nitrogen was carried by Drs. Weiler and Strauss of Oxford. The melting points of these complexes are uncorrected.

Conductometric titrations were carried by using precision measuring Bridge Type WBR, No. 106 with logarithmic indicator amplifier Type TAV, IKc No. .034, manufactured by Wissenschaftlich Technische Werkstätten Wieltheim/Oby., Germany.

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